

Structuralist Approach in Literary Research

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Abstract:

Structuralist approach seeks to understand a thing in the context of larger structures to which it belongs. It studies the underlying principles by which a work of art exists. It gives primacy to pattern or structure over substance. In order to understand or analyze the structure of anything, we have to break the whole into parts and examine how the parts are related. Such method when applied to a literary work proves to be effective since it helps us understand the basic elements or parts of which it is made and the relation between these parts. Such method is commonly known as “structural analysis” or “analysis of structure” in the parlance of literary criticism. Vladimir Propp, A. J. Greimas, Levi Strauss, Tzvetan Todorov, Gerard Genette, Roland Barthes, and many literary critics attempted structural analysis of literary works. The present paper discusses their models of structural analysis and how they can be incorporated in literary research.

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Broadly speaking, structuralism is a science that tries to comprehend how “systems work”. It implies that nothing can be “understood individually”; things have to be looked at as a “part of larger structures to which they belong”. Structuralism seeks to describe the “underlying principles” (Dobie: 151) by which a work of art exists. These larger structures include language, myths, rituals, folklores etc. Structuralism originated from the seminal book of Ferdinand Saussure before the First World War. It encompasses variety of disciplines from linguistics through literary criticism to history, anthropology and sociology. It appeared in France in around 1050s with the great works of the anthropologist Claude Levi Strauss and the literary and cultural critic Roland Barthes. Following these writers many critics contributed to the corpus of structuralism. Louis Althusser, Lucien Goldmann, Gerard Genette, Todorov, Jacques Lacan and Janathan Culler were some of the notable names among them. They were all interested in

structure or system that can be studied synchronically rather than diachronically i.e. its historical development over the years. They were not interested in meaning but something that makes the meaning possible, that is, in form rather than content. For them the world without ‘structure is meaningless- a random and chaotic continuum of possibilities. What structures do is to order that continuum, to organize it according to a certain set of principles, which enable us to make sense of it. In this way, structures make the world tangible to us, conceptually real, and hence meaningful’ (Simon Malpas et al: 4). The “structure” is, thus, given primacy over substance in structuralism.

The term ‘structure’ is such a common concern of literary artists, literary theorists and critics, philosophers, sociologists, anthropologists, and engineers that there are many attempts at defining it. It is simply used to suggest arrangement of parts. Etymologically, the word is a derivation from ‘Old French, or Latin *structūra* or *struere* meaning ‘to put together’ or ‘to build’ or ‘to organise’ or ‘to fit together’¹. The whole is constituted by arranging the parts together in a certain way i.e. structure. In order to understand or analyze the structure of anything, we have to break the whole into parts and examine how the parts are related. Such method when applied to a literary work proves to be useful since it helps one understands the basic elements or parts of which it is made and the relation between these parts. Such method is commonly known as “structural analysis” or “analysis of structure” in the parlance of literary criticism. Vladimir Propp, A. J. Greimas, Levi Strauss, Tzvetan Todorov, Gerard Genette, Roland Barthes, and many literary critics attempted structural analysis of literary works. The present paper discusses their models of structural analysis and how they can be incorporated in literary research.

Structuralism, as mentioned earlier, is indebted to the theories of Saussure whose seminal book *Course in General Linguistics* (French 1916) provided the necessary theoretical framework. *La langue* and *la parole* are the two important terms introduced by Saussure in his synchronic approach to semiotic system. *La langue* (meaning tongue in French) refers to the system as language possessed and adopted by members of a particular language community. *La parole* (meaning speech or word in French) is the actual manifestation of the system or language in speech and writing. *Langue* is abstract whereas *parole* is its concrete manifestation. Finally we

¹ www.dictionary.reference.com

can say the distinction between these two is the distinction between code and message, or structure and performance. To be fully realized, the latter has to follow the rules of the former.

Many structuralist ideas can be traced back to the Russian Formalism as derived through the Prague School. The classical example of earlier attempts at studying the system that produces meaning through various functions is Vladimir Propp's *Morphology of the Folktales* (1928). He tried to generalize features or functions across texts and concentrate on the system generating meaning which is not specific to individual work. Roland Barthes and Levi Strauss furthered the method of systematizing any semiotic system for that matter. Claude Levi-Strauss chalks out the steps of structural analysis in *Structural Anthropology*. The first step of structural analysis, according to him, is the definition of constituent units or elements of a system at hand. And the second step is to define the 'relationships of oppositions, and correlation and permutation and transformation among these elements' (SA: x). The structural analysis, thus, involves two processes: first is the identification of constituent elements (parts) of a system as a unified whole and second is to how these elements relate to each other and how they fit together to form a particular configuration.

Attempts at 'Structural analysis' long preceded the advent of 'Formalism' and 'Structuralism'. Aristotle in his *Poetics* (fourth century B. C.) discussed the structural aspects of a literary work. He used the term *mythos* for structured literary expression and thus laid the foundation for the so called structuralist approach to literature. He considers the 'arrangement of the particular actions' as the 'prime and most important element of tragedy' (CLC: 60). In his account of the structure of dramatic plots, Aristotle discussed four possible plots structures: simple plots, plots with peripety, plots with discovery, and plots with both peripety and discovery. Unlike the structuralist critics who do not offer their preferences for the variable structural patterns which are capable of generating all possible imitations, Aristotle considered the last type as the best among the four.

According to Alan Dundes, there are two types of structural analyses: syntagmatic and paradigmatic. The example of the first is Vladimir Propp's *Morphology* in which he has studied 'the chronological order of the linear sequence of elements' (*Morphology*: xi) in Russian folktales. The syntagmatic analysis describes the 'horizontal plane' of narrative. The second type of structural analysis attempts to describe the 'pattern' (drawn from the 'a priori binary principle

of opposition' (ibid)) underlying the text of a folktale. Here, the elements are separated from the sequence and are reorganized in a kind of 'analytic schema'. The paradigmatic relation, thus, describes the 'vertical plane' of the narrative. Claude Levi Strauss championed the second type of analysis.

Vladimir Propp's famous study of Russian tales entitled as '*Morphology of the Folktale*' appeared in 1928 and 30 years later in English. He studies the nature of narratives, in a particular group of Russian folk tales. The word 'morphology' signifies the study of structures or forms, a process of observing components in a system and examining, how they relate to one another. Propp too studies the structures of these tales with the same method. He rejects the earlier attempts to study folktales in terms of their historical origin or themes or types of characters as they, according to him, lead nowhere. Hence, he develops a morphology in which he isolates the essential components of a tale and observes how they relate to each other.

Propp studies the folktales in terms of the functions of its various characters. By "function", he means both the actions of characters and the consequences and implications of these actions for the story. He says:

Function is understood as an act of a character, defined from the point of view of its significance for the course of the action (*Morphology*: 21). To Propp a function, thus, is the basic unit of the narrative 'language' and refers to the important actions which construct the narrative. To him, there are only a limited number of functions i.e. thirty one. A single tale may not contain all 31 functions. So also, there are many subcategories within given functions. Hence, the possibility of many different combinations of functions is immense. Besides, the sequence of functions as occurred in folktales and fairy tales is identical. That is, all these tales have the same structure.

Another example of the syntagmatic structural analysis is Freytag's pyramid. To Gustav Freytag, a drama always portrays a 'struggle' (104) in which the hero fights against the opposing forces. Freytag based his model on Aristotle's theory of tragedy. It is known as 'a pyramidal structure' (114) or Freytag's pyramid. He describes five points of dramatic structure; each part corresponds to an angle or a vertical side. He describes:

It (action) rises from introduction with the entrance of the exciting forces to the climax, and falls from here to the catastrophe'. Between these parts three parts lie

(the parts of) the rise and the fall. Each of these five parts may consist of a single scene or a succession of connected scenes, but the climax is usually composed of one chief scene (114-15).

The Paradigmatic Structural Analysis tries to identify the various paradigms underlying the manifest content of texts. These models enable perspective and choice, difference and oppositions of sets of signifiers. Models of Structural analysis given by Claude Levi-Strauss and A. J. Greimas are examples of the paradigmatic analysis. Claude Levi-Strauss (1908) applied the linguistic model developed by Structural linguistics to different aspects of social life of primitive people. Linguistics provided him with etymologies to establish between certain kinship terms relationships which were not so immediately apparent. He borrowed some of the ideas of structuralism such as the study of larger structures i.e. langue, concept of system, binary opposition and discovering general rules through inductive or 'logical' deductive method (SA: 33). His structural analysis of kinship terms informs us about his views on social structure of primitive people. Kinship systems are found in all societies. They refer to sets of rules regarding who may or may not marry whom and prescribing the nature of filial relationships (Hawkes: 35). Levi Strauss treats these systems as linguistic systems. While discussing the kinship system, he says: 'like phonemes, kinship terms are elements of meaning; like phonemes they acquire meaning only if they are integrated into systems' (SA: 34). And in order to grasp its structure, each relation should be considered as a part of a system and that system should be conceived as a whole.

A. J. Greimas (1912-1992) proposed his 'actantial model' (Semantique Structural: 1985:174-180 and 192-212) based on the theories of Vladimir Propp and Claude Levi Strauss. He attempts to describe the narrative structure of action as depicted in literary works with the actantial model. In this model, the selected action may be broken down into six components, called actants. These actants are then fitted into three actantial categories (the three sets of binary oppositions). These categories produce all the actors of any actions. The six actants are 1) the Subject (for example, the Prince), 2) the Object (the rescued Princess), 3) the Sender (the King), 4) the Receiver (the Prince), 5) the Helper (the Magic Sword) and 6) the Opponent (the Dragon or Witch).

The combination models involve both the syntagmatic and paradigmatic approaches. They look at story as having a more or less fixed sequential structure on the one hand, and accommodating variability through substitutions and interdependency on the other hand.

Todorov's "Structural Analysis of Narrative" and Roland Barthes' "Introduction to the Structural Analysis of Narratives" (1977) provide us with the models which combines both these models.

Structural study of literary text is an interesting area of research. It gives primacy to structure or pattern over substance. It relates the study of individual works to larger structure to which they belong. It also gives us a more objective understanding of the text. In that sense, structuralism is as one of the important approaches to study literature and language.

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